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Cascadia Liquefaction Hazard Maps for Scenario Planning and Rapid Response: Partnering Around Community Data and Mechanics-Informed AI

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Cascadia Liquefaction Hazard Maps for Scenario Planning and Rapid Response: Partnering Around Community Data and Mechanics-Informed AI

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Abstract

Soil liquefaction poses a significant threat to the built and living environments, necessitating accurate predictions for community planning and emergency response. This study addressed a critical gap in CRESCENT research, focusing on the Partnerships and Applications pillar. Employing community data and mechanics-informed artificial intelligence (AI), we developed an improved regional liquefaction hazard model. These models were designed to convolve with any "ShakeMap" to predict the probability of liquefaction at high resolution and with near-real-time capability. This flexibility enables partners to tailor the resulting liquefaction hazard maps for various locations, spatial extents, earthquake events, and purposes, and to integrate the predictions with public and agency-specific inventories (e.g., demographic information and infrastructure data). Crucial to the success of the project was collaboration with partners to enhance the regional specificity of the AI model. A substantial expansion of Cascadia-specific subsurface training data was used to train the AI model and anchor its predictions to reality in the field via kriging. Liquefaction hazard maps for specific earthquake scenarios, coupled with user-friendly software, enable partners to create products that meet their diverse needs. This project aligned with CRESCENT's mission by fostering collaboration across agencies, compiling valuable data for future research, and delivering improved hazard maps to diverse stakeholders. The project's ambitious goals were made possible by data and investments from multiple partners, underscoring the importance of leveraging collective resources to enhance regional resilience.

1. Did you accomplish what you set out to with this project?

Yes. The project accomplished its primary objectives by (i) developing a new geospatial liquefaction model, enhanced with region-specific data from Cascadia, and (ii) applying this model to generate scenario-based hazard maps for an array of earthquake events in the U.S. Pacific Northwest.

1.1 Model Development

Reliable soil liquefaction predictions are required for pre-event planning and mitigation, and for post-event response and recovery. However, state-of-practice liquefaction models rely on subsurface geotechnical data such as cone penetration test (CPT) measurements, limiting the ability to make predictions at high spatial resolution across the regional extents impacted by large earthquakes. To address this, the development and use of "geospatial" liquefaction models has grown in recent decades. In general, geospatial models infer subsurface conditions (e.g., soil thickness, density, saturation, etc.) without subsurface measurements by way of geospatial proxy variables (e.g., mapped topographic parameters or surface geology). Recent literature has advanced geospatial liquefaction modeling, and tests of geospatial and CPT-based models underscore both the promise and limitations of geospatial approaches. We observe that existing geospatial liquefaction models tend to: (1) directly predict liquefaction without consideration of liquefaction mechanics; (2) not consider subsurface geotechnical data, when available; (3) use relatively few geospatial inputs; (4) rely on statistical methods insufficient for modeling nonlinearities; and/or (5) use emergent AI methods but are rife with methodological or implementation issues.

This project presented a new geospatial liquefaction modeling framework designed to overcome these limitations. Rather than predicting manifestations, we trained surrogate models that mimic predictions of geotechnical, mechanistic models at locations of CPT data. These surrogate models leveraged a wide library of geospatial data, employed AI to capture complex and nonlinear relationships, and incorporated local geostatistical updating where subsurface data are available. To enable rapid, large-scale deployment, we precomputed expected liquefaction responses for all potential earthquake scenarios and stored the expected response as mapped parameters that await ground-motion information from a real or scenario earthquake of interest.

Subsurface data and geotechnical model predictions are central to our approach, both for AI model training and to locally update AI predictions with measured data. Rather than relying on liquefaction observations alone, we use in-situ tests (i.e., CPT measurements), which vastly increases the potential training set because sites need not have experienced an earthquake. With the rise of community data repositories, this disparity between the number of available geotechnical tests and liquefaction case history observations will grow. We compiled 37,000 profiles from 48 U.S. states and 19 countries, including data from international compilations, Italy, New Zealand, and the United States, plus newly digitized CPTs with a predominant focus on the U.S. Pacific Northwest.

Each CPT was standardized (e.g., aligned tip and sleeve data, interpolated missing measurements) and subjected to synthetic seismic loading spanning peak ground accelerations (PGAs) of 0.05–2.0 g and earthquake magnitudes of 4.5–9.0. Liquefaction triggering factors-of-safety were computed with the state of practice Idriss & Boulanger (2008) model. To predict consequences of liquefaction at the ground surface, the results from triggering analysis were input to three geotechnical manifestation models: liquefaction potential index, LPI (Iwasaki et al., 1978), a modified LPI, termed LPI_{ISH} (Maurer et al., 2015), and liquefaction severity number, LSN (van Ballegooy et al., 2014). These models each output a “vulnerability” or manifestation index, which are used in hazard mapping, land-use planning, and engineering site-assessment to predict a soil profile’s cumulative liquefaction response, or damage potential, at the ground surface. The resulting relationship between a manifestation index and magnitude-scaled PGA (PGA_M) is a unique signature of each site. Towards predicting this signature remotely, we fit a simple functional form to the data:

$$MI(PGA_M) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{for } PGA_M < 0.1g \\ A * (\tan^{-1}(B * (PGA_M - \frac{A/100}{B})^2)), & \text{for } PGA_M \geq 0.1g \end{cases} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

where MI is the manifestation index (i.e., LPI, LPI_{ISH}, or LSN), PGA_M is as previously defined, A and B are independent fitting parameters that will be predicted by AI, and \tan^{-1} is expressed in radians. In this function, A generally describes the MI attained at high PGA_M and B generally captures the sensitivity of the response to ground shaking (Fig. 1). Further, because A and B are event-independent, they are herein predicted globally in advance of an earthquake, enabling rapid, low-cost computation of LPI, LPI_{ISH}, and LSN when one occurs. With these products, users may employ existing fragility functions conditioned on MIs to predict the probability of certain outcomes. In this project, we adopt the fragility functions of Geyin and Maurer (2020) for predicting liquefaction surface manifestation (i.e., “ground failure”).

Although liquefaction is best modeled via mechanics, the link between geospatial variables and subsurface conditions is empirical. While domain expertise can guide variable selection, there is no expectation these variables will map neatly onto soil properties in a strictly mechanistic way. We ultimately selected 37 global variables through an iterative process evaluating correlation structures, variable importance, model performance, overfitting behavior, and expert judgment. Unlike other geospatial models, these variables are not required for end-user model execution; the final predictions are stored as mapped parameters: A and B. The chosen variables – which include topographic and hydrologic data (e.g., height

above drainage, distance to rivers) and outputs from other models (e.g., clay fraction) that collectively approximate soil thickness, saturation, density, and typology – were sampled at 37,000 CPT sites.

Fig. 1. Example LPI_{ISH} versus PGA_M curves for four sites.

We then employed AI techniques to empirically exploit this predictive information, taking care to avoid the serious flaws common in most existing AI liquefaction models. Several types of AI algorithms were used to train provisional models, during which the training (90%), cross-validation (ten-fold), and test (10%) set performances were judged for performance and overfitting behavior. Ultimately, we developed bagged decision trees models (i.e., A and B models for LPI, LPI_{ISH} , LSN), with hyperparameters optimized via mean-squared-error loss. The trained models were applied to predict A and B at ~ 90 m resolution (~ 0.000833 degrees). High-performance computing was required to sample geospatial data (over 1 TB) and implement the models at ~ 1.3 billion locations. Next, predictions A and B were updated near CPT sites using regression kriging, where residuals were used to anchor predictions to known subsurface conditions. These residuals decay toward zero (the mean residual for all models) with distance from the CPT via semivariogram functions. These models will ultimately be judged in the context of predicting liquefaction in future earthquakes. To this end, we tested model predictions using three case history libraries. We quantified model performance with the Brier Score (BS) and bootstrapped the BS results 10,000 times to derive confidence intervals. Results showed statistically significant improvements over existing geospatial models, including those currently adopted by USGS. Overall, the findings from these tests strongly support adopting and further scrutinizing the resulting AI models.

1.2 Scenario Hazard Mapping

The models can be deployed either at discrete locations or across the extent of an affected area, and predictions can be made either in near-real-time after an event using recorded ground motions, or in planning for a scenario event using predicted motions. A scenario represents one realization of a potential earthquake by estimating ground motions for an assumed fault-rupture magnitude, location, and geometry. Scenarios are commonly used in planning, coordinating emergency response, and examining exposure of infrastructure at regional scale. The USGS has nearly 800 scenario ground-motion simulations for the continental U.S. In this project, we employed all available scenarios for finite-fault ruptures in the states of WA and OR to conduct regional hazard and impact forecasting. We simulate 85 scenarios in total from three USGS catalogs: (i) the Building Seismic Safety Council 2014 Event Set; (ii) the ShakeMap Scenario Catalog for Quaternary Active Faults in Washington State; and (iii) the M9 Cascadia Earthquake Scenarios (CSZM9). We also simulate the 2nd, 16th, 50th (median), 84th, and 98th percentile ground motions (i.e., 5 “scenarios”) from the CSZM9 catalog. This catalog contains the ensemble ShakeMaps of Wirth et al. (2021) depicting thirty M9.0 Cascadia Subduction Zone (CSZ) ruptures as simulated by Frankel et al. (2018).

To simulate the 85 scenarios, we adopt the USGS ShakeMap ground motions (i.e., PGA) in .xml format. We convert the ShakeMap PGA into a raster and scale it to PGA_M . Given these inputs for each scenario, we surrogated the three geotechnical models (i.e., LPI , LPI_{ISH} , and LSN) and computed the corresponding probability of liquefaction-induced ground failure (“PGF”) using the fragility functions of Geyin and Maurer (2020). PGF represents the median probability of observing liquefaction manifestation at any location within a map pixel. Finally, because the surrogated geotechnical models have different efficacies and it is unclear which model is best (e.g., Geyin et al., 2020; Rasanen et al., 2023), we average the three PGFs in each pixel for an “ensemble” model. The resulting products are provided in an online repository in both GIS and PDF formats. As an example, predictions for a scenario M9.0 rupture of the CSZ are shown in Fig. 2 near Portland, OR and Seattle, WA.

Fig. 2. Predicted PGF for a scenario M9.0 rupture of the CSZ (median scenario) near (a) Portland, OR and (b) Seattle, WA.

Collectively, the 85 modeled scenarios included crustal, intraslab, and Cascadia subduction zone events, reflecting the full seismic hazard spectrum in the region. The resulting maps provide (1) high-resolution forecasts of liquefaction probability across the region; and (2) Open-access GIS products suitable for diverse applications including land-use planning, infrastructure risk assessment, insurance modeling, and emergency response. Collectively, these two studies fully realized the goals of the proposal: expanding Cascadia-specific subsurface training data, advancing the science of geospatial liquefaction modeling, and delivering scenario-based hazard maps for broad stakeholder use.

2. If not, what did you do differently and how did you account for the changes?

The work proceeded as planned and achieved the core goals. The only difference that might be of interest is that while the original proposal anticipated that a *Cascadia-specific* model might substantially outperform global models, the results showed that the advantages of learning from larger global datasets often outweigh the benefits of regional specialization. The local data compiled from

Cascadia is still of utmost importance because it ground truths the AI predictions via regression kriging, such that the AI prediction is scaled up or down to match that predicted by a geotechnical model at the site of an in-situ test.

3. What is the next step for development of this project / priority?

Our immediate next step is to use the scenario hazard maps in infrastructure impact simulations, particularly for road networks. This extension is underway in a follow-on study which couples the liquefaction hazard maps with transportation network data to evaluate road service disruptions, closures, and cascading effects on regional mobility following Cascadia megathrust earthquakes. Other near-term priorities include: (1) Integrating the maps into traffic simulation and evacuation modeling, to quantify emergency response constraints and resilience gaps. (2) Expanding to multi-hazard frameworks by combining liquefaction forecasts with coseismic landslide and tsunami models for comprehensive impact assessment; and (3) Continuing to grow community-accessible CPT databases in Cascadia and beyond, ensuring the models remain current and anchored to field data.

4. Where did you publish/present on this work?

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5. Conclusion

This project successfully advanced the state of liquefaction hazard forecasting by creating and applying a new class of mechanics-informed, machine learning-based geospatial models. The work not only delivered improved Cascadia-specific hazard maps but also produced a scalable modeling framework with global applicability. The next phase of work, which includes quantifying cascading infrastructure impacts, has already begun, positioning this research to directly inform resilience planning and emergency response in the Pacific Northwest and beyond.

6. Select References

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